

Republic of the Philippines
UNIVERSITY OF RIZAL SYSTEM
Rodríguez, Rizal

In collaboration with

BARANGAY SAN ISIDRO, RODRÍGUEZ, RIZAL

Survey Instrument

This research, entitled **“Eco-Guilt and Eco-Responsibility in Solid Waste Management Practices: Evidence from a Philippine Local Community,”** was conducted for academic purposes only.

In accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, all information you provide will remain strictly confidential. The data will be used solely for statistical analysis and the development of the study. No personal information (such as full name or exact address) will be disclosed. All data will be stored securely and will be destroyed after the completion of the research.

Your participation is voluntary, and you may withdraw or refuse to answer at any time without any negative consequences. There is no physical or psychological risk in participating in this study. By answering this form, you are freely giving your consent for your responses to be used for academic purposes.

You will answer the questions in the data-gathering instrument, and you may also be interviewed regarding this important topic if selected.

I understand that the purpose of this study is to explore the attitudes and behaviors of residents regarding solid waste management, particularly in terms of eco-guilt and eco-responsibility.

My participation is voluntary, and I may withdraw or refuse to answer any question at any time without any negative consequences. All information I provide will remain confidential and will be used solely for academic purposes in accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

By completing this questionnaire and participating in the interview if selected, I voluntarily agree to take part in this study and give permission for my responses to be used for research purposes.

Name and Signature

Date

Demographic Profile:

Gender: _____

Age: _____

Years of residency: _____

Nature of Work: _____

Part I: Please place a check (✓) in the appropriate box.

Indicate the level of solid waste management practices of the respondents based on the following aspects. Kindly mark the number that corresponds to your HONEST OPINION regarding the statements.

Scale	Meaning	Description
5	Strongly Agree	Always practiced and consistently demonstrates excellent waste management behavior.
4	Agree	Frequently practices proper waste management behavior.
3	Neutral / Undecided	Sometimes practiced; not consistent.
2	Disagree	Rarely or almost never practices proper waste management behavior.
1	Strongly Disagree	Never practices proper waste management behavior.

Waste Management Practices Among Households in Terms of Reduce, Reuse, Recycle, and Recover/Dispose

	5	4	3	2	1
Reduce					
1. I choose products with little or no plastic packaging.					
2. I avoid buying things that I do not really need.					
3. I make an effort to consume all the food so that nothing is wasted.					
4. I prioritize using products sold in bulk rather than individually packaged ones to reduce waste.					
5. I show others the proper ways to reduce the use of plastic and paper.					
Reuse					
1. I use my own containers (tumbler, lunch box, eco bag) instead of disposable ones.					
2. I keep bottles, jars, or boxes so they can be reused.					
3. I repurpose old items (e.g., old clothes as cleaning rags).					
4. I allow my family to reuse items instead of throwing them away immediately.					
5. I show others the benefits of reusing items.					
Recycle					
1. I segregate biodegradable, non-biodegradable, and recyclable waste.					
2. I participate in or support recycling programs in the barangay or school.					
3. I create simple recycled crafts (e.g., plant pots made from bottles).					
4. I give bottles, cans, and paper that can still be recycled to junk shops.					
5. I take part in school or barangay activities that promote recycling awareness.					
Recover					
1. I dispose of waste at the proper time and in the designated containers.					
2. I use the barangay's designated Materials Recovery Facility (MRF).					
3. I practice composting of biodegradable waste (if space is					

available).					
4. I ensure that no waste is thrown into canals, roads, or rivers.					
5. I follow the barangay's "No Segregation, No Collection" policy.					

Part II: Please place a check (✓) in the appropriate box.

To determine the level of eco-guilt or feelings of remorse among residents regarding their waste management and environmental practices, kindly mark the number that corresponds to your HONEST OPINION regarding the following statements.

Scale	Meaning	Description
5	Strongly Agree	I fully believe, feel, or practice the statement; I have a strong and clear sense of conviction or emotion.
4	Agree	I often believe, feel, or practice what is stated in the statement.
3	Neutral / Undecided	I sometimes feel or do this; I am not fully sure or it does not always apply to me.
2	Disagree	I rarely feel or practice what is stated; I do not fully believe it.
1	Strongly Disagree	I do not believe or practice what is stated; it is contrary to my feelings or views.

Level of Eco-Guilt Among Households

Emotional Discomfort	5	4	3	2	1
1. I feel guilty when I do not properly segregate my household waste.					
2. I feel guilty when I use more plastic than necessary.					
3. I feel guilty when I engage in behaviors that contribute to littering.					
4. I experience a sense of guilt when I engage in improper waste disposal practices.					
5. I feel guilty when I fail to fulfill my responsibility in proper waste management.					
Awareness of consequences					
1. I recognize that disposing of waste improperly can seriously harm human health.					
2. I am aware that poor waste management significantly damages the environment.					
3. I understand that throwing garbage into rivers or canals contributes to flooding.					
4. I am concerned about the potential impact of poor waste management on future generations.					
5. I take into account the negative effects on my community when I fail to segregate waste properly.					
Moral Accountability					
1. I believe it is my responsibility to manage my waste properly.					
2. I think it is wrong not to contribute to proper waste management.					
3. I feel accountable when I fail to follow proper waste disposal practices.					
4. I consider it my obligation to demonstrate correct waste management behavior.					

5. I feel responsible for taking action when I witness improper waste disposal practices.					
Social Pressure Guilt					
1. I feel uneasy when others see me disposing of waste improperly.					
2. I feel embarrassed when neighbors criticize me for improper waste practices.					
3. My reputation is affected when I do not practice the 4Rs.					
4. I worry that others will respect me less if I litter.					
5. I feel ashamed when I do not keep my surroundings clean in front of my family or friends.					

Part III: Please place a check (✓) in the appropriate box.

To determine the level of eco-responsibility (social responsibility toward the environment) on their waste management and environmental practices, kindly mark the number that corresponds to your HONEST OPINION regarding the following statements.

Level of Eco-Responsibility Among Households

Sense of Moral Duty	<i>5</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>1</i>
1. I consider it my duty to protect the environment through proper waste management.					
2. I regard following the 4Rs (reduce, reuse, recycle, recover) as a moral obligation.					
3. Being responsible for waste is part of who I am.					
4. I believe it is wrong not to support the community's cleanliness programs.					
5. I feel responsible for teaching others proper waste management practices.					
Proactive Commitment					
1. I voluntarily participate in the community's cleanliness programs.					
2. I do not wait for others before properly disposing of waste.					
3. I take steps to reduce waste even without being instructed.					
4. I personally take the initiative to recycle or reuse materials.					
5. I offer suggestions on how to improve waste management in the community.					
Community Accountability					
1. I believe I have a responsibility to my community regarding waste management.					
2. I join community or school clean-up activities.					
3. I help neighbors understand the importance of waste segregation.					
4. I encourage my family and friends to practice proper waste management.					
5. I see myself as part of the solution to my community's waste problems.					
Consistency of Behavior					
1. I consistently practice waste segregation.					
2. I am disciplined in disposing of waste properly wherever I am.					
3. Even when busy, I make sure to follow proper waste disposal					

practices.					
4. I regularly follow community waste management rules.					
5. I maintain good waste management habits even when no one is watching.					

Thank you for participating in this study. Rest assured that your data will be kept with strict confidentiality.

The Researcher